

An aerial photograph of a river winding through a green landscape. In the foreground, there is a large array of blue solar panels. In the background, several boats are docked along the riverbank.

2021 ANNUAL REPORT

BUILDING SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE
IN EUROPE & BEYOND

A large, stylized white graphic of a flower or leaf, composed of several overlapping leaf-like shapes, positioned in the lower half of the cover.

SCIENCE
EUROPE
Shaping the future of research

**SCIENCE
EUROPE**
Shaping the future of research

Colophon

June 2022

**2021 Science Europe Annual Report:
Building Scientific Excellence in Europe and Beyond**

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6702209

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“Founded in 2011, Science Europe has grown into a respected and influential voice in the European research policy debate.”

FOREWORD

In what was another challenging year, research continued to play a crucial role in generating scholarly knowledge and addressing societal and global challenges. The swift development of COVID-19 vaccines through extraordinary international collaboration illustrates the great capacity of response of our research systems.

For Science Europe, 2021 was a very important year: the association celebrated its 10th year of existence. Founded in 2011, it has grown into a respected and influential voice in the European research policy debate. Moreover, we published a new Strategy Plan for 2021–2026, which maps our collective objectives and sets a specific yet flexible action framework over the next five years.

The Strategy takes into account the new societal and political changes that shape the evolution of research in the European Research Area and globally. It provides a solid basis to support our mission “to define long-term perspectives for European research and champion best-practice approaches, ensuring high-quality science for the benefit of humanity and the planet.” It will further strengthen the profile of Science Europe in research policy making and facilitate research organisation including new areas such as research culture and the role and contribution of science in society. I would like to thank the Science Europe Member Organisations for their engagement in shaping this strategic development.

The present Annual Report highlights the most significant contributions throughout 2021. Knowledge sharing and a true European spirit among our members shape up our positions and guidelines. These cover a wide variety of facets of research organisation and research policy making, including management of research data, EU data-related legislation, Open Science, research infrastructures, research ethics and integrity. We also closely followed up the launch of Horizon Europe and firmly advocated the full association of the UK and Switzerland to the new Framework Programme. Our common vision on research culture, published in November, drives now our actions to foster a more productive and efficient research system, centred around the quality of the research process, in full support for scientific autonomy and the promotion of diversity and inclusion.

MARC SCHILTZ
SCIENCE EUROPE PRESIDENT

I would like to thank my colleagues in the 2019–2021 Governing Board for their guidance and constructive discussions, and congratulate the new members who took office in November 2021. For me, it is an honour to have been trusted to lead the association with them, supported by the Secretary General and the Office in Brussels. I would also like to thank the many partners we collaborated with, including the OECD, EUA, ALLEA, CESAER, ISCN, cOAlition S, and the Global Research Council. Our achievements would not be possible without the collegial collaboration with our partners in the wider research community and stakeholder groups.

I look forward to another year of excellent collaboration with our Member Organisations and partners whose commitment, expertise, and engagement form the foundation of the legitimacy and success of our joint activities. We also look forward to strengthening the dialogue with the EU institutions and at global level through the Global Research Council and other international fora.

Marc Schiltz
Science Europe President

GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS 2019-2021

Marc Schiltz
President
Secretary General of the
Luxembourg National
Research Fund (FNR) –
Luxembourg

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(FORMAS) – Sweden

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Council (VR) – Sweden

Melanie Welham
Executive Chair,
UK Research and
Innovation (UKRI) –
United Kingdom

Antonio Zoccoli
President of the
National Institute for
Nuclear Physics (INFN) –
Italy

SCIENCE EUROPE 2021 - OUTPUTS AT A GLANCE

OUTPUTS AT A GLANCE 2021

Q1

JANUARY

- Covid-19 Virtual European Regional meeting of the Global Research Council (GRC)
- 2nd edition of the [Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management](#)

FEBRUARY

- Launch event of [Horizon Europe](#), the new EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (R&I), co-hosted by Manuel Heitor, Portuguese Minister of Science, Technology and Higher Education

MARCH

- [Scientific Networking Workshop on Covid-19](#) with the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC)
- [Statement on the Participation of Associated Countries in Horizon Europe](#)
- Science Europe invited to be part of the [agreement drafting group on research assessment reform](#), following European Commission consultation workshops on research assessment
- [Open Access Diamond Journals Study](#), the first in-depth report that uncovers the vast size of the Diamond Open Access scholarly publishing system

APRIL

- Meeting relevant EU decision makers and advocating the agreed [Horizon Europe budget](#) to be maintained in its entirety
- Setup of a Science Europe Task Force to assess member organisations' efforts to support different aspects of [cross-border collaboration](#)

MAY

- [First high-level exchange](#) with Governing Board Members of Science Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC)
- Briefing paper on [Open Access Monitoring](#)
- [Research infrastructures mobilisation in response to Covid-19](#) meeting organised with the OECD-Global Science Forum (GSF)
- Survey to identify data collection practices in research on [equality, diversity, and inclusion](#), with a focus on gender equality, developed by the Gender Working Group of the Global Research Council (GRC)
- [Advocating researchers' rights in Open Access](#) with other partners

JUNE

- [Strategy Plan and Multi-annual Action Plan for 2021–2026](#)
- [Practical Guide to Sustainable Research Data](#)

Q2

JULY

- [Statement on the inclusion of all European R&I powers in the ERA development process](#), supporting full association of Switzerland, Norway, Iceland, and the United Kingdom to Horizon Europe
- [Reaction to the Commission Proposal for a Council Recommendation on a Pact for Research and Innovation](#)

AUGUST

- Input provided to the legislation on EU digital agenda on [European Digital Principles](#) and the role of research in [Public Interest Data Use](#)

SEPTEMBER

- Launch of the [recognition systems of research project](#) and setup of a dedicated Science Europe Task Force on the topic
- Setup of [new Science Europe Working Groups](#) dedicated to the Green and Digital Transition, Communication, Research Culture, and Open Science

OCTOBER

- Contribution to the thematic debate on [research infrastructures](#) during the 'New ERA' conference' on 26–27 October 2021
- [Becoming a member of ESFRI Stakeholder Forum](#)
- [2021 GRC Regional Meeting](#) on 'Science and technology workforce' and 'Research ethics, integrity and culture in the context of rapid research results'

NOVEMBER

- [High Level Workshop on ERA: Research Culture in the ERA](#) and 10th anniversary celebration of Science Europe
- [Statement on research culture](#), calling for an ERA that fosters a prospering research system where researchers can thrive
- [Statement on the involvement of stakeholders in the ERA governance](#)
- [Statement on a successful UK association to Horizon Europe](#)
- [Symposium on the Net-Zero Transition](#), linking research and education to tackle the climate crisis in the context of COP26
- [High-level event exploring lessons learned on science-policy processes](#) in the context of COP26

DECEMBER

- [Policy workshop on interdisciplinary research and research assessment](#) with the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC)

Q4

Q3

MAP OF SCIENCE EUROPE MEMBERS

MAP OF SCIENCE EUROPE MEMBERS

RESEARCH FUNDING ORGANISATION
 RESEARCH PERFORMING ORGANISATION

STRATEGY PLAN

“Reinforcing its profile through an expanded mandate, addressing research culture and what science contributes to society.”

Marc Schiltz, President

SCIENCE EUROPE'S STRATEGY (2021-2026)

A defining year for Science Europe, 2021 was the year its new strategy was unanimously endorsed by its Member Organisations. This strategy came at a time when the need to adapt was never greater for research ecosystems: in the wake of the Covid-19 pandemic, and facing climate change and an accelerated digital transition.

Science Europe's new Strategy Plan (2021-2026) was designed to support its Member Organisations in their mission to generate world-class scientific knowledge, for the advancement of knowledge and to benefit our societies. It paved the way to support European research for the next five years and coincided with the launch of Horizon Europe, the 9th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (R&I), and a renewed focus on the European Research Area (ERA).

THE SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN (2021-2026)

THREE STRATEGIC PRIORITIES ENCAPSULATE OUR VISION

SHARING

ALIGNMENT

COLLABORATION

ADVOCACY

OUTREACH

Science Europe's Strategy Plan has a set of three Strategic Priorities encapsulating its vision: 'Shape European research policy developments'; 'Contribute to the evolution of research culture'; 'Strengthen the role and contribution of science in tackling societal challenges' (see diagram).

A series of Framework Actions within the three central priorities are related in the dedicated [Multi-annual Action Plan](#).

To serve these strategic goals and objectives, Science Europe has set up six thematic Working Groups, some renewed, some entirely new. The policy development regarding the European Research Area, is integrated in all areas of work, as well as the global dimension of research.

Both the Strategy and the Multi-Annual Action Plan are true to the shared effort by and extensive consultation of Member Organisations between 2019 and 2021. It is therefore a testimony to the collective contribution by Science Europe's Member Organisations, the Governing Board, and the Office.

SCIENCE EUROPE DEDICATED MULTI-ANNUAL ACTION PLAN

COVID-19

COVID-19

“2021 testified to the marvel of science in saving millions of lives, through rapid development and deployment of Covid-19 vaccines.”

Melanie Welham, Governing Board Member

In challenging circumstances, Science Europe Member Organisations were leading research organisations in response to the crisis. Rapidly recalibrating processes and practices, they upheld crucial support for researchers helping them respond to, mitigate, and recover from this pandemic.

Science Europe and Member Organisations' Activities

Follow-up survey on the activities, actions, and measures by Member Organisations

Over the last two years, the Covid-19 pandemic impacted all aspects of our lives. Research organisations faced the challenges of social and travel restrictions like many others and, in parallel, looked for research-led responses and solutions to the crisis.

In early 2021, Science Europe updated its 2020 survey into the measures implemented by Member Organisations as a response to the persisting impact of Covid-19. Outcomes of this survey indicated that, despite unprecedented disruptions, research organisations were able to rapidly re-orient their processes and practices. They were able to maintain their support for research and researchers, whilst also launching many new initiatives to respond to, mitigate, and recover from the pandemic. Member Organisations effectively implemented fast-track calls for proposals, adaptations to online research assessment processes, and means to support heavily impacted groups such as early-career researchers. Based on the many lessons learnt from this global crisis, research organisations are still taking further measures to improve their preparedness for future crises.

International Collaboration

Science Europe did not limit the remit of its activities to that of its Member Organisations. It extended its outreach to the international research community and exchanged regularly on the impact of the pandemic and its potential consequences on the global research ecosystem.

In this context, in partnership with the German Research Foundation (DFG), Science Europe co-hosted the Covid-19 Virtual European Regional meeting of the Global Research Council (GRC). Held on 14 January 2021, this event allowed major science funding and performing bodies to learn from each other in developing their responses to the crisis and in mitigating the impact of the pandemic on their core business. The conference also re-affirmed the role of researchers as providers of scientific evidence, leaving policy decisions to relevant political authorities. Participants called for more effective science advice systems. A [report of the event](#) was one of the documents framing the discussion at the 9th GRC Annual Meeting in Durban, co-hosted online in May 2021 by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) and the South African National Research Foundation (NRF).

Furthermore, together with the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC), on 4 March Science Europe organised a Scientific Networking Workshop on Covid-19, bringing together a hundred researchers from Europe and China to discuss social consequences, social behaviours, impact on care systems and society at large. This event, a follow-up of the previous year's workshop on prevention of Covid-19, demonstrated the continuing collaboration between Science Europe and NSFC (see section on [International Collaboration](#)).

What has become clear since 2020 is the remarkable adaptability of researchers, research organisations, and research systems as a whole.

ACTIVITY AREAS

SHAPE EUROPEAN RESEARCH POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

“At the heart of Europe’s ambition lies the European Research Area.”

Sven Stafström, Governing Board Member

“A successful and innovative European Research Area must foster brain circulation and capitalise on the strong research collaboration built between countries in the last four decades.”

Zbigniew Błocki, Governing Board Member”

European Research Area

Science Europe’s vision for the ERA is one with optimal conditions, bolstering robust education, research and innovation systems; an area where science underlies sustainable economic, environmental, and societal development.

Science Europe Statements and Reactions on the ERA

On 16 July, the European Commission adopted its proposal for a [Council Recommendation](#) on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe (Pact for R&I) to support the implementation of national ERA policies.

Science Europe published a series of strategic positions, with a focus on the [Pact for R&I](#), the involvement of stakeholders in the [ERA governance](#) system, and core issues for research. In a [joint open letter](#) with other pan-European stakeholders, the association called for the meaningful and inclusive involvement of stakeholders in the governance of the European Research Area. Science Europe regretted the lack of researchers’ involvement in the Commission proposal, calling for a more structured and systemic approach to engaging stakeholders in the Pact for R&I.

The fact that global outreach and co-operation with third countries featured in the Pact for R&I was welcomed. However, Science Europe repeatedly called for the [United Kingdom](#) and [Switzerland](#) to be included in the ERA developments even if association to the EU Framework Programme would not be politically possible.

Its intense advocacy on the role of stakeholders in the ERA Governance bore fruit: following the adoption of the [Council Conclusions](#) on the new ERA and Pact for R&I, Science Europe was welcomed to the ERA Forum, a new working group bringing together representatives of Member States and Stakeholders that is integrated in the ERA governance.

Building on the 2020 High Level Workshop’s discussions on “The ERA Contribution to the post-Covid-19 Recovery and Transition to a Resilient Society”, hosted by the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) in Portugal, Science Europe engaged in dialogue with the 2021 Presidencies of the Council of the EU: the Portuguese Ministry for Science, Technology and Higher Education, and the Slovenian Ministry of Education, Science and Sport.

Input provided by Science Europe was developed in close consultation with the Governing Board, and its High-Level Policy Network, which now covers ERA-related matters in addition to its existing cross-border collaboration focus.

SHAPE EUROPEAN RESEARCH POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

Horizon Europe

Science Europe's Member Organisations bring to the table a unique wealth of knowledge and expertise for the EU to tap into, when shaping flagship R&I European Framework Programmes such as Horizon Europe.

EU's 2022 Budget for Horizon Europe

The Horizon Europe legislative process was finalised in April 2021. Throughout, Science Europe kept a close watch on the legislative process and set up a registry of the activities and calls to be launched in each instrument of the programme. Over the reporting period, the association met relevant Members of the European Parliament which served to maintain regular exchange with the Parliament's Committee on Industry, Research and Energy (ITRE). At the same time, it provided input to the dialogue between the European Commission, Parliament, and EU Council and pushed for the agreed Horizon Europe budget to be maintained in its entirety.

Participation of European Non-EU Countries in Horizon Europe

Deadlocked since mid-2021, discussions on the association of Switzerland and the UK to Horizon Europe prompted strong reactions by Science Europe and other stakeholders. In addition to specific calls mentioned in the previous section, in partnership with main stakeholders in R&I and education, Science Europe sent a [letter](#) to European Commission President Ursula Von der Leyen and several Directorates-General, calling for a rapid and full association of the UK to Horizon Europe.

In March 2021, the European Commission and Member State representatives limited eligibility of Associated Countries in specific calls that were seen as strategic to maintaining the EU's industrial independence (quantum and space R&I). Science Europe issued a [statement](#) resisting these limitations and highlighting the need for collaboration with the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) countries, members of the European Economic Area (Norway, Iceland, and Liechtenstein), Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. The statement stressed that the collaboration benefits far outweighed the identified risks on the EU's strategic independence.

Dialogue with the European Commission on Horizon Europe instruments

Through its dedicated Working Group on Horizon Europe, Science Europe regularly engaged in discussions with Commission officials. Specific topics of discussion were the opportunities for researchers and fundamental research in the European Innovation Council, ERA implementation, and implementation of the Missions and the European Partnerships. Other issues debated included the launch of the new action supporting collaboration between national programmes, how to involve the European Parliament in the implementation of Horizon Europe, and how Horizon Europe can contribute to the EU Health Strategy in the context of Covid-19.

“Advocating EU institutional policy developments to ensure the best participation conditions by Science Europe Member Organisations in Horizon Europe.”

Antonio Zoccoli, Governing Board Member

**SHAPE
EUROPEAN
RESEARCH
POLICY
DEVELOPMENTS**

“Advocating the best conditions for research for the long-term perspectives for European R&I, through sustained collaboration with EU institutions, ensuring highest quality of science.”

Ingrid Petersson, Vice-President

EU Legislation

As the representative of the collective interest of its members, Science Europe drives its influence on EU research-related legislation proposals from its long-standing status as trusted and reliable partner.

Science Europe contributed to several EU legislative initiatives that will impact the research sector in the years to come. One main initiative was the Regulation on a single market for digital services: the EU [‘Digital Services Act’](#). Science Europe joined forces with several organisations to argue for an exemption for not-for-profit scientific and educational repositories (the [Confederation on Open Access Repositories](#) (COAR), the [European University Association](#) (EUA), the [Association of European Research Libraries](#) (LIBER), and [SPARC Europe](#)).

Another important legislative proposal to which Science Europe contributed was the Regulation on Data Governance: the EU [‘Data Governance Act’](#). The association advocated to the European Parliament requesting some changes on two specific issues: the scope of confidential data and the inclusion of established sector-specific standards in the future legislation.

Still within data-related legislation, Science Europe further responded to Commission-led consultations in preparation of future initiatives, including the EU [‘Data Act’](#), underlining that research plays an essential role in the use of data in the public interest, and the ‘Declaration on European Digital Rights and Principles’, highlighting that broader consideration of the benefits of research for society and economy is needed.

Concerning the proposal for a regulation on Artificial Intelligence (the [‘Artificial Intelligence Act’](#)), Science Europe called on the Commission to focus also on research and not exclusively on industry and business players. Any future legislation on AI liability should be easily adaptable and needs to strike the right balance between supporting innovation and fostering trust.

Upon thorough analysis of all proposals, regular exchanges were maintained with EU institutional representatives, namely European Commission, European Parliament and the Research Attachés of the Permanent Representations to the EU, advocating the views of its members. On the occasion, this was done together with like-minded stakeholder organisations, to strengthen the outreach of the research sector. Expert input and legislative amendments proposals were prepared in consultation with Member Organisations and the Working Group on Data Sharing and Supporting Infrastructures.

CONTRIBUTE TO THE EVOLUTION OF RESEARCH CULTURE

Research Culture

Research culture covers the behaviour, values, expectations, attitudes, and norms of any research system. Science Europe and its Member Organisations collectively aspire to bring about positive culture shifts to create attractive and sustainable research ecosystems where researchers can truly thrive.

The 2021 High Level Workshop, co-organised by Science Europe, the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR) and the Luxembourg Ministry of Higher Education and Research, reflected on the research culture underpinning research activity and explored ways to keep the research sector attractive for current and future generations of researchers. A [report of the workshop](#) was published in December 2021.

Furthermore, the new Working Group on Research Culture provided input to a [Statement on Research Culture](#) which was adopted in the framework of the High Level Workshop. The statement calls for an ERA that focuses on the quality of research and its processes, supports scientific freedom, and promotes social diversity and inclusion. It acknowledges that these conditions will, in turn, foster a productive research system. It also calls for an open values framework and stressed the importance of revisiting the incentive and rewards framework. Participants of the High Level Workshop discussed a first concept for such a 'values framework', identifying as value clusters autonomy, integrity and transparency; diversity and equality; inclusion, collaboration and collegiality; openness; communalism; and, trust.

Science Europe committed to further developing a leadership role in promoting actionable changes to improve the attractiveness and sustainability of European research systems, in particular highlighting system values, reviewing research and integrity practices, addressing the reform of research assessment systems, and promoting gender and diversity in research. The first two issues will be addressed in 2022, while the last two were part of the 2021 Workplan, as summarised below.

“Empowering researchers through a prospering research system.”

Rosa Menéndez, Vice-President

CONTRIBUTE TO THE EVOLUTION OF RESEARCH CULTURE

Research Assessment and Recognition Systems

Despite well-known limitations, many research assessment systems still focus heavily on journal-based indicators. Science Europe advocates value-centred recognition systems instead. These systems need to evolve, not only to safeguard the quality of science but also to institute positive research cultures.

Developing Recognition Systems for Qualitative and Healthy Research

A new project on the recognition systems of research was launched in 2021, building on work done under the previous 'Quality of Science' priority and on activities conducted in 2019 and 2020 on [research assessment processes](#). The project's ambition was to spark a reflection on research recognition towards value-centred research systems, as opposed to systems with output-based indicators. This work was facilitated by a dedicated Task Force on Recognition Systems.

Seeking to promote high quality and sustainable research systems, Science Europe developed a scoping questionnaire on research culture to investigate its Member Organisations' opinions on the topic. This consultation was seen as an important starting point in the journey undertaken by the association towards a collective understanding of how diverse research culture-related aspects are. Outcomes of this survey could be summarised as follows:

“Spearheading multi-partner dialogue on common values for improved research assessment systems for the ERA and globally.”

Marc Schiltz, President

A first online workshop was hosted by the Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ), featuring five prominent researchers from the Croatian research system. The workshop outcomes will be included in the Task Force's reflections as it develops policy recommendations in 2022.

Science Europe in the Drafting Group on a European 'research assessment reform'

Science Europe took part in three consultations with stakeholders on research assessment reform organised by the European Commission, where it put forward its views on research assessment processes based on its work described in the section above. Furthermore, in partnership with the European University Association (EUA), Science Europe engaged in collective advocacy on a reform based on the May 2019 [joint statement](#). This statement already presented a shared vision to develop a wider range of criteria to reward and incentivise research quality as the fundamental principle of scholarly research, and ascertain assessment processes and methods that accurately reflect the vast dimensions of research quality and credit all scientific contributions appropriately.

A [scoping report by the European Commission](#) was published in November, following extensive consultation with universities and research organisations, including Science Europe members. The scoping report provided evidence that sustained the vision by EUA and Science Europe and both organisations were invited by the Commission to lead the drafting of an agreement on the reform of research assessment; an initiative that is taking shape in 2022.

**CONTRIBUTE
TO THE
EVOLUTION
OF RESEARCH
CULTURE**

“Fighting all forms of discrimination, bias, harassment and bullying within research communities.”

Angelika Kalt, Governing Board Member

Gender and Diversity

Science Europe argues for a research environment where all scholars can reach their fullest potential, irrespective of gender, sexual orientation, religion, disabilities, ethnic origin, or social background.

Discrimination in academia is first and foremost detrimental to researchers who experience it, as it does not only affect their mental health, but also damages the whole research system.

In 2021 Science Europe continued its work in this area as co-chair of the [Gender Working Group](#) of the Global Research Council (GRC). In line with the 2016 ‘[Statement of Principles and Actions: Promoting the Equality and Status of Women in Research](#)’, the Working Group developed a survey to identify data collection practices on gender in research. A [report](#), drafted by researchers from Stellenbosch University, was launched during the [2021 GRC Annual Meeting](#). The report showed that, while over 80% of the funding organisations worldwide collected gender-related data in project-funding applications, only a small number of funders collected data related to other aspects of grant management process (and these were mainly in Europe).

The data gathered inspired guidelines for research performing and research funding organisations and encouraged further work to prevent gender-based and sexual violence, harassment based on race, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, gender identity and expression, along with disability; work that will be presented in 2022.

The limitations in developing appropriate and reliable benchmarks for data gathering and the need to find new ways of including soft factors for gender and diversity policy development were discussed in the Gender Summit 2021 (Berlin 14-16 April), where Science Europe moderated a panel of eminent experts, some of them preparing a hallmark publication expected in 2022.

In parallel, Science Europe kept up its contribution to the Funders for Gender Equality Community of Practice ([FORGEN](#)), promoting fairness and equality in research assessment processes. Through FORGEN, Science Europe set up a strong knowledge base of initiatives promoting gender equality throughout the research funding process, linking its contribution with that in the framework of the GRC’s Working Group.

STRENGTHENING THE ROLE AND CONTRIBUTION OF SCIENCE IN TACKLING SOCIETAL CHALLENGES

“Promoting the role of science in shaping sustainable development beyond 2030.”

Rosa Menéndez, Vice-President

The Green and Digital Transition

Society has high expectations for science to provide solutions to societal challenges. Science Europe and its Member Organisations push for the curiosity-driven and challenge-oriented research needed to tackle these challenges.

In line with its third Strategic Priority to “strengthen the role and contribution of science in tackling societal challenges”, Science Europe facilitated exchange on science-policy mechanisms and interdisciplinary research for the green and digital transition through a newly dedicated working group.

First Science Europe event on Science Policy for the Green Transition

An accompanying event of the Slovenian Presidency of the Council of the EU, the workshop ‘[Science for the Green Transition](#)’ (7 September) brought forward different science-policy perspectives to speed up the transition towards climate neutrality. Co-organised with CSIC, FORMAS, and UKRI, the workshop prepared for the UN COP26 climate change conference. Key messages were published in a [report](#) in November 2021.

Science Europe Activities in the framework of COP26

Held in partnership with [CESAER](#), the [International Sustainable Campus Network](#) (ISCN), and the University of Strathclyde, the ‘[Science for Zero-Net Transition](#)’ event (8 November) discussed actions that research organisations and universities can take to help realise the Net-Zero transition.

A ‘[Call to Action](#)’ to research organisations presented a vision of “a world where research and education communities work together and in interaction with industry and society at large to solve urgent global challenges.” It proposed six framework areas for collective action, including creating an interdisciplinary perspective on Net-Zero challenges, and equipping the next generation of students and researchers to deal with them.

In a [High-Level Panel](#) co-organised with UKRI (10 November), eminent science-policy experts discussed how lessons learned from the Covid-19 pandemic could help address climate change and adaptation. Featuring a keynote speech by Manuel Heitor, Portuguese Minister of Science, Technology and Higher Education, it highlighted that research organisations, particularly funders, should reward policy-oriented research activities and promote international collaboration with research performers, whilst mitigating hurdles.

Science Europe will continue to advocate the role of research in addressing climate change in COP events and with other suitable European and international bodies.

CROSS-CUTTING TOPICS

“Making open science the new norm in research, opening the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation, and communication.”

Thierry Damerval, Governing Board Member

Open Science

2021 marked the start of a new agenda to tackle the transition to Open Science in all its dimensions, pivoting from its long-standing focus on Open Access (OA) to research publications and data.

Open Access to research publications

In May 2021, Science Europe published a briefing paper: [‘Open Access Monitoring: Guidelines and Recommendations for Research Organisations and Funders’](#), driven by the Working Group on Open Access to Research Publications (which operated until September 2021). In addition, Member Organisations were regularly updated on the Open Access policy in [Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement](#), on the release of the [Open Research Europe publication platform](#), together with the expected European Commission activities in the framework of the new European Research Area.

The landmark [‘Open Access Diamond Journals Study’](#) (March 2021), led by [OPERAS](#), commissioned by [cOAlition S](#) and co-funded by Science Europe, was the first in-depth report uncovering the vast size of the Diamond Open Access scholarly publishing system, which is free for authors and for readers. While providing recommendations for sustainability, the study started a movement towards enforcing Diamond Open Access, led by Science Europe, the French National Research Agency (ANR), cOAlition S and OPERAS. The movement continues in 2022, bringing aboard a growing number of organisations.

Other aspects of Open Access to research publications were also addressed: Science Europe supported authors’ rights retention through a [joint statement](#) with CESAER and the European University Association (May 2021). An [open letter](#) by cOAlition S on rights retention and publisher equivocation was also co-signed (April 2021). Beyond Open Access to journal publications, Science Europe further signed a [call to action for Open Access to academic books](#) (May 2021).

Open Access to research data

In January 2021, Science Europe published an [extended edition](#) of the ‘Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management’ and, in June 2021, published a [‘Practical Guide to Sustainable Research Data’](#). Both guides were produced in collaboration with key stakeholders including research performing and funding organisations, universities, and research infrastructures.

CROSS-CUTTING TOPICS

At EU level, after the creation of the European Open Science Cloud legal entity ([EOSC Association](#)) in December 2020, Science Europe changed its status to that of an Observer to represent the collective views of its Member Organisations who are also members of the EOSC Association. Throughout 2021, Science Europe contributed to the [EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA), co-drafted Terms of Reference of two new Task Forces (on research careers, recognition, and credit; on long-term data preservation). Science Europe is now a member of these two Task Forces, which began regular activity from October 2021.

Moving towards Open Science

The transition to Open Science includes Open Access to research publications, data, and other types of output as well as opening up the entire research process. While Open Access remains high on the agenda, it is part of a more comprehensive effort that also considers other aspects such as research assessment systems, research infrastructures, policy and legislation, and investment and finance.

As made evident in this report, Science Europe is already active in all these fields and will bring them closer together in 2022 and beyond. To this end, a conference on Open Science on 18–19 October 2022 will take place. The goal of this comprehensive event is to bring together institutional leaders, researchers at all stages of their careers, and experts from the field to discuss two main questions: is Open Science ready to become the norm in research? How do we ensure an equitable transition to Open Science? The event will build on the ‘UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science’ that Science Europe has supported as an international framework with the potential to drive the global discussion on moving towards Open Science.

“Promoting good practices, with a focus on links between national, EU, and international Research Infrastructures for large-scale projects.”

Ingrid Petersson, Vice-President

Research Infrastructures

Investing in Research Infrastructures (RIs) is key for the global research ecosystem. Science Europe works so that the funding, management, and operation of national RIs are both approached from a collaborative and internationally co-ordinated mindset.

Collaboration with the OECD-Global Science Forum

Building upon recommendations in the 2020 joint Science Europe/OECD-Global Science Forum (GSF) [policy paper](#), a workshop entitled “[Research Infrastructures mobilisation in response to Covid-19: lessons learned](#)” (May 2021), was organised by the two partner organisations, ahead of the International Conference on Research Infrastructures ([ICRI 2021](#)). The workshop allowed a debate on the challenges and the measures needed to be taken by policy makers in the context of a global pandemic, such as Covid-19. It also was an opportunity to discuss lessons learnt to improve their efficiency. The [workshop’s outcomes and key messages](#) were presented at ICRI 2021. Furthermore, Science Europe committed to join a new project led by OECD-GSF to identify specific issues of relevance to ‘Very Large Research Infrastructures’, to be developed in 2022.

Contribution to ERA developments on Research Infrastructures

Building on its expertise in the area, Science Europe became a member of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures ([ESFRI Stakeholders Forum](#)). It also actively contributed to the thematic debate on ‘research infrastructures’, in the context of the ‘[new ERA conference](#)’ (October 2021). Science Europe promoted the value that its Member Organisations bring to Research Infrastructures, enabling RIs to build efficiently, responsively, internationally, and at scale. It also advocated a necessary review of the outdated [2016](#) European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures.

Research Infrastructures and Covid-19

The [report](#) of the European Regional Global Research Council event on Covid-19 specified the need to create more robust data management plans and co-ordinated policies for infrastructures. The Science Europe work on research data management guides (*See section on [Open Science](#)*) aims to support funders and performers in this endeavour. Funding to create and maintain platforms and other infrastructures for data and sample collection, as well as to ensure quality control and standardisation of data and samples, are much needed.

CROSS-CUTTING TOPICS

“Fostering model guidelines and standards for international, cross-border research collaboration.”

Roland Fischer, Governing Board Member

International Collaboration

As globalised research systems are getting more and more complex, optimal collaboration becomes a precondition for well-functioning research.

Since its launch in 2020, [Weave](#), a bottom-up cross-European initiative developed by national research funders in Europe, and supported by Science Europe, allows the development of multilateral research projects involving two or more funding agencies. It aims to simplify the submission and selection procedures of research proposals by researchers from different countries through a single evaluation procedure and a common set of framework policies. Weave brings together 12 national and regional research funders, with the possibility to include other funders in the future.

In parallel, Science Europe started an internal project led by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) on monitoring the added value of cross-border collaboration. Carried out in co-operation with the High-level Policy Network, a Task Force gathering Member Organisation representatives with expertise in international collaboration and monitoring systems was generated. The task force has been discussing characteristics of cross-border collaboration and will identify relevant elements to monitor (expected in 2023).

At the same time, Science Europe’s Governing Board, with the support of the High-level Policy Network, continued to foster bilateral international collaboration, mainly with the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC). In March, a scientific networking workshop dedicated to Covid-19 issues was co-organised by the two partners (*see section on [Covid-19](#)*). At a subsequent meeting between the Governing Boards (May 2021), collaboration was deemed helpful by the respective Presidents. Collaboration continued with a workshop on the topics of interdisciplinary research and on research assessment (7–8 December). The workshop was an opportunity to reflect on the different concepts and practices in these two areas. Activities will continue in 2022.

Global Research Council

The [Global Research Council](#) (GRC) is a virtual global forum that brings together Heads of Research Councils around the world. Many Science Europe Member Organisations take part in GRC-related activities at regional and/or global levels, with Science Europe leading the co-ordination of European activities.

Science Europe co-ordinates the GRC European Regional meeting. All GRC regions organised their respective meetings and held elections in May 2021. According to the topics addressed, two Statements of Principles on [Mission-oriented Research](#) and [Public Engagement](#) had been endorsed by GRC participant organisations in September 2020, following extensive consultation with GRC participants and Governing Board. The [2021 GRC Annual Meeting](#) was organised by South Africa’s National Research Foundation (NRF) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). Science Europe Member Organisation and DFG’s President, Professor Katja Becker, was elected as a European member and Chair of the GRC Governing Board.

In preparation for the 2022 GRC Annual Meeting, the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Poland’s National Science Centre (NCN), and Science Europe co-organised the [European Regional GRC Meeting](#) (October 2021). The event acted as a platform for European participants in the GRC to discuss key aspects of ‘Research ethics, integrity and culture in the context of rapid research results’ and of ‘Science and technology workforce’. This preparatory meeting promoted Member Organisations’ best practices, including the [‘CSIC Code of Good Scientific Practices’](#). The discussions contributed to the preparation of the two corresponding Statements of Principles to be adopted at the 2022 GRC Annual Meeting in Panama, hosted by the National Science Foundation (NSF, United States) and the National Secretariat of Science, Technology and Innovation (SENACYT, Panama).

“Science is vital in addressing global societal challenges, as recognised by the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The GRC is therefore needed to facilitate this fundamental contribution.”

Marc Schiltz, President

COMMUNICATION

COMMUNICATION

“Facilitating Science Europe’s and Member Organisations outreach activities, whilst promoting science through targeted communication.”

Lidia Borrell-Damián, Secretary General

Communicating science is crucial if society is to gain a better grasp of the importance of research. Science Europe worked with its Member Organisations to strengthen the role that research institutions play when it comes to science communication.

Communication and information flows between Science Europe and its Member Organisations were fostered to enhance the visibility of activities and messages. Science Europe renewed its communication efforts, better and more frequently promoting Member Organisations’ activities and the work of the association across the three strategic priorities.

In addition, Science Communication emerged as a new priority area in itself in the framework of the Strategy Plan 2021–2026. Science Europe committed to “lead, participate in, and communicate activities promoting the value of scientific research: for its own sake and for societal, cultural, economic, and democratic development.” In close collaboration with the newly established Working Group on Communication, Science Europe initiated work with its Member Organisations to reinforce the collective capacity to communicate research more effectively and enhance communication of science to society.

The work was organised around two main topics to be developed in 2022: communication for science policy purposes, and designing joint communication campaigns over selected areas to reinforce the dialogue between science and society.

2021 IN NUMBERS

SCIENCE EUROPE PUBLICATIONS

40

As part of its commitment to improve visibility and discoverability of outputs, and in line with its policy recommendations on research data, the Science Europe Office began the process of attributing Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to its publications and hosting them on the Open Access repository Zenodo.

POLICY POSITIONS GUIDELINES & REPORTS

12K+

 DOWNLOADS

26

HIGH LEVEL PRESS MENTIONS

Science Europe continued to gain regular exposure in the press in dedicated research and policy news outlets on a wide range of topics. It targeted these outlets as key influencers and multipliers in the research policy sphere.

MAJOR EVENTS ORGANISED

8

The shift to digital events and online webinars also allowed the association to record and share presentations and discussions from the events through social media (such as COP26-related events), increasing its digital outputs and reaching out to new audiences.

SCIENCE EUROPE SOCIAL MEDIA VIEWS & FOLLOWERS

Social media platforms also saw an increased number of followers and views, which improved Science Europe’s external visibility.

1,1M+

 IMPRESSIONS

10K+

 FOLLOWERS (+9%)

87K+

 IMPRESSIONS

4K+

 FOLLOWERS (+10%)

SCIENCE EUROPE WEBSITE

44K+

 VISITORS

141K+

 PAGE VIEWS

PUBLIC NEWSLETTER

[July 2021](#)
[December 2021](#)
[Subscribe](#)

VIDEOS

[Member Organisations share their vision for Research Culture in ERA](#)
[Science Europe Webinars playlist](#)
[Science for Net-Zero Transition playlist](#)

“Anticipating yet another vibrant and active decade, Science Europe and its Member Organisations stand ready for the first implementation year of its new Strategy in 2022.”

AFTERWORD

In 2021, Science Europe’s new Strategy Plan prepared us to strengthen our position as a leading voice for the European research and innovation systems. We increased our membership among research funding and research performing organisations, and expanded our range of topics to include research culture, the role and contribution of science in society, and science communication.

Shaping European research policy remains a main priority. We are very pleased that Science Europe is one of the stakeholders in the ERA Forum and thus able to address the needs of research organisations with the Member States and the European Commission. We look forward to following up the implementation of Horizon Europe and, importantly, advocating the inclusion of all European countries in the ERA.

In 2022, Science Europe will increase support to its members in the area of research culture. We will start by developing a common framework of the values underpinning the organisation of research systems, based on the position published in November 2021. Furthermore, we will work on research assessment and recognition systems; on equality, diversity, and inclusion policies; research integrity and ethics; and research careers.

To reinforce the pivotal role of science in tackling societal challenges, planned activities in 2022 include the identification of interdisciplinary research programmes and success factors for science policy that addresses the green and digital transitions. We aim to realise the Call to Action that we published in November, together with our partners.

Our conference on Open Science in late 2022, open to all, and in line with the UNESCO Recommendation, will take stock of progress so far and identify key actions needed in the research systems to make Open Science a widespread practice. We also foresee that 2022 will see an important upgrade in Science Europe’s communications.

I would like to thank our members for their continuing constructive engagement and the Governing Board for their continuing direction and support. I also commend the efforts of the Science Europe Office staff, who are essential to realising our objectives.

Together with our Member Organisations, we will continue to share best practices, facilitate alignment, collaborate, advocate and promote policies to enhance research systems for the benefit of the scientific endeavour and of society. The year 2021 has drawn one decade to an end, and our second decade is only just dawning.

LIDIA BORRELL-DAMIÁN
SCIENCE EUROPE
SECRETARY GENERAL

ANNEX

SCIENCE EUROPE GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS

FULL GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS 2021

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Marc Schiltz (President)	Secretary General of the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Ingrid Petersson (Vice-President representing RFOs)	Director General of the Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Rosa Menéndez (Vice-President representing RPOs)	President of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Zbigniew Błocki	Director of the National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Thierry Damerval	President/CEO of the French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Roland Fischer	Vice-President of the German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Angelika Kalt	Director of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Sven Stafström	Director General of the Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Melanie Welham	Executive Chair, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Antonio Zoccolì	President of the National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy

GOVERNING BOARD ELECTIONS NOVEMBER 2021: INCOMING MEMBERS

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ángeles G. Borrego	Vice-President of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Adrian Curaj	Director General of the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Matthias Koenig	Vice-President of the German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Marcel Levi	President of the Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Mari Sundli Tveit	Chief Executive of the Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway

GOVERNING BOARD ELECTIONS NOVEMBER 2021: OUTGOING MEMBERS

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Zbigniew Błocki	Director of the National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Roland Fischer	Vice-President of the German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Rosa Menéndez	President of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Ingrid Petersson	Director General of the Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Sven Stafström	Director General of the Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden

MEMBERS OF SCIENCE EUROPE'S COLLABORATION GROUPS

HIGH-LEVEL POLICY NETWORK ON THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA AND CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ignacio Baanante	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
Sebastiaan den Bak	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Jean-Luc Barras	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Marta Barrionuevo	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
Linda Bell	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development	Sweden
Reinhard Belocky	Austrian Science Fund	Austria
Mojca Boc	Slovenian Research Agency	Slovenia
Jasminka Boljevic	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Priya Bondre-Beil	German Research Foundation	Germany
Lidia Borrell-Damián (Chair ERA)	Secretary General Science Europe	Belgium
Helena Burg (Chair CBC)	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Adrian Curaj	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania	Romania
Kristin Danielsen	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Elena Domínguez	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Dominique Dunon-Bluteau	French National Research Agency	France
Antoaneta-Victoria Folea	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania	Romania
Joël Groeneveld	Fund for Scientific Research	Belgium
Johanna Hakala	Academy of Finland	Finland
Kate Hamer	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Maja Horst	Independent Research Fund Denmark	Denmark
Rudolf Kučera	Czech Science Foundation	Czech Republic
Joyce Kuipers	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Andrew Macdonell	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Teresa Maguire	Health Research Board	Ireland
Irena Martinović Klarić	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Anu Noorma	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Myriam Poll	German Research Foundation	Germany
Kinga Słomińska	Foundation for Polish Science	Poland
Edmunds Tamanis	Latvian Science Council	Latvia
Laura Tejada	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Stefan Törnqvist	Swedish Research Council	Sweden
Maira Torrent	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Isabelle Verbaeys	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Rune Vistad	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Wolfgang Wachter	German Research Foundation	Germany

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Paul Wiley	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Justyna Woźniakowska	National Science Centre	Poland
Gonçalo Zagalo Pereira	Foundation for Science and Technology	Portugal
Science Europe Coordination	Adrien Braem (ERA) - Mathilde Reumaux (CBC)	

WORKING GROUP ON HORIZON EUROPE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Jānis Ancāns	Latvian Science Council	Latvia
Reinhard Belocky	Austrian Science Fund	Austria
Inga Benner (Co-Chair)	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Jasminka Boljević	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Sarah Bühler	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Britta Fängström	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development	Sweden
Francesco Ferlino	National Institute for Nuclear Physics	Italy
Rüdiger Hesse	Max Planck Society	Germany
Sylwia Kostka	National Science Centre	Poland
Joyce Kuipers	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Hannele Lahtinen	Academy of Finland	Finland
Anne Lindeløv	Independent Research Fund Denmark	Denmark
Maria Lindholm (Co-Chair)	Swedish Research Council	Sweden
Berta Martínez	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Tom-Espen Møller	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Rui Munhá	Foundation for Science and Technology	Portugal
Richard Nakath	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Ülle Napa	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Maria Nash	Science Foundation Ireland	Ireland
Pierre-Olivier Pin	French National Research Agency	France
Cristina Rodríguez	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
Esther Rodríguez	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
Joaquín Serrano	Spanish State Research Agency	Spain
Elena Simion	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania	Romania
Adrienn Szendrey	Eötvös Loránd Research Network	Hungary
Krisztina Szepesvári	Eötvös Loránd Research Network	Hungary
Maira Torrent	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Karin Totland	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Ann Van Hauwaert	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Rune Vistad	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Martin Winger	German Research Foundation	Germany
Natacha Wittorski	Fund for Scientific Research	Belgium
Science Europe Coordination	Mathilde Reumaux	

WORKING GROUP ON DATA SHARING AND SUPPORTING INFRASTRUCTURES until September 2021

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Fernando Aguilar	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Zoé Ancion	French National Research Agency	France
Laura Bandura-Morgan	National Science Centre	Poland
Tommaso Boccali	National Institute for Nuclear Physics	Italy
Isabel Bolliger	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Patricia Clarke	Health Research Board	Ireland
Geraldine Clement-Stoneham	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Maria Cruz	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Sanja Halling	Swedish Research Council	Sweden
Harri Hautala	Academy of Finland	Finland
Alina Irimia	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania	Romania
Tom Jakobs	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Hans de Jonge	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Artūras Kaklauskas	Research Council of Lithuania	Lithuania
Sharon Kappala	Health Research Board	Ireland
Jean-Claude Kita	Fund for Scientific Research	Belgium
Filipa Pereira	Foundation for Science and Technology	Portugal
Katharina Rieck	Austrian Science Fund	Austria
Michael Royeck	German Research Foundation	Germany
Ramunė Rudokienė	Research Council of Lithuania	Lithuania
Anne Elisabeth Søsnes	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Cornelia Sommer	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Mark Thorley	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Johanne Thorup Dalgaard	Danish Council for Independent Research	Denmark
Joaquín Tintoré	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Alexandra Vandervelde	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Barbara Wajnchold	Foundation for Polish Science	Poland
Stefan Winkler-Nees (Chair)	German Research Foundation	Germany
Science Europe Coordination	Marie Timmermann	

WORKING GROUP ON OPEN ACCESS until September 2021

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Zoé Ancion	French National Research Agency	France
Laura Bandura-Morgan	National Science Centre Poland	Poland
Lovorka Barać Lauc	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Marion Boland	Science Foundation Ireland	Ireland
Georg Botz (Chair)	Max Planck Society	Germany

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Petr Chorošenin	Czech Science Foundation	Czech Republic
Patricia Clarke	Health Research Board	Ireland
Tommy Dahlén	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare	Sweden
Alina Irimia	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania	Romania
Hans de Jonge	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Jean-Claude Kita	Fund for Scientific Research	Belgium
Ingmars Kreismanis	Latvian Council of Science	Latvia
Marika Meltsas	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Joana Novais	Foundation for Science and Technology	Portugal
Laura Patrizii	National Institute for Nuclear Physics	Italy
Irmantas Pečiūra	Research Council of Lithuania	Lithuania
Tobias Philipp	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Agnès Ponsati Obiols	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Marte Qvenild	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Paul Richards	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Katharina Rieck	Austrian Science Fund	Austria
Astrid Sängler	German Research Foundation	Germany
Lisbeth Söderqvist	Swedish Research Council	Sweden
Guy Thoonen	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Jussi Varkemaa	Academy of Finland	Finland
Science Europe Coordination	Mathilde Reumaux	

WORKING GROUP ON OPEN SCIENCE

from September 2021

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Zoé Ancion	French National Research Agency	France
Lourdes Armesto	Spanish State Research Agency	Spain
Lovorka Barać Lauc	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Andreas Björke	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life & Welfare	Sweden
Tommaso Boccali	National Institute for Nuclear Physics	Italy
Georg Botz	Max Planck Society	Germany
Rachel Bruce	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Dejana Carić	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Petr Chorošenin	Czech Science Foundation	Czech Republic
Maria Cruz (Chair)	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Tommy Dahlén	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life & Welfare	Sweden
Martine Garnier	French National Research Agency	France
Julián Garrido	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Sanja Halling	Swedish Research Council	Sweden
Harri Hautala	Academy of Finland	Finland

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Alina Irimia	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania	Romania
Tom Jakobs	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Matthias Katerbow	German Research Foundation	Germany
Ole Kirk	Independent Research Fund Denmark	Denmark
Jean-Claude Kita	Fund for Scientific Research	Belgium
Arnis Kokorevičs	Latvian Science Council	Latvia
Siri Lader Bruhn	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Laura Mackey	Science Foundation Ireland	Ireland
Joke Meeus	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Annalisa Montesanti	Health Research Board	Ireland
Lissa Nordin	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development	Sweden
Joana Novaris	Foundation for Science and Technology	Portugal
Simon Ošo	Slovenian Research Agency	Slovenia
Aneta Pazik-Aybar	National Science Centre	Poland
Tobias Philipp	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Agnès Ponsati	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Elena Primo	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
Marte Qvenild	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Katharina Rieck	Austrian Science Fund	Austria
Priit Tamm	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Wiktoria Wojtyra	Foundation for Polish Science	Poland
Science Europe Coordination	Bregt Saenen	

WORKING GROUP ON RESEARCH CULTURE

from September 2021

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Lillian M. Baltzrud	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Olivier Boehme	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Priya Bondre-Beil	German Research Foundation	Germany
Carolina Cañibano (Co-Chair)	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Giorgio Chiarelli	National Institute for Nuclear Physics	Italy
Anne Cody	Health Research Board	Ireland
Rosário Costa	Foundation for Science and Technology	Portugal
Frances Downey (Co-Chair)	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Rochelle Fritch	Science Foundation Ireland	Ireland
Pilar Gayoso	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
Kasper Gossink	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Tobias Grimm	German Research Foundation	Germany
Laurence Guyard	French National Research Agency	France
Miklós Györfi	Eötvös Loránd Research Network	Hungary
Jon Holm	Research Council of Norway	Norway

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Inger Jonsson	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life & Welfare	Sweden
Arnis Kokorevičs	Latvian Science Council	Latvia
Marta Łazarowicz-Kowalik	Foundation for Polish Science	Poland
Irena Martinović Klarić	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Sandra Milovanović Soldatić	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Katrin Milzow	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Eva Molíková	Czech Science Foundation	Czech Republic
Luis Montoliu	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Lissa Nordin	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development	Sweden
Emma Olsson	Swedish Research Council	Sweden
Sonja Ochsenfeld-Repp	German Research Foundation	Germany
Helen Post	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Falk Reckling	Austrian Science Fund	Austria
Irene Sánchez	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
Sean Sapcariu	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Birgit Schiøtt	Independent Research Fund Denmark	Denmark
Audrey Ségérie	Fund for Scientific Research	Belgium
Ioana Spanache	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania	Romania
Zsuzsanna Steinczinger	Eötvös Loránd Research Network	Hungary
Ewelina Szymańska-Skolimowska	National Science Centre	Poland
Kata-Riina Valosaari	Academy of Finland	Finland
Science Europe Coordination	James Morris	

WORKING GROUP ON THE GREEN AND DIGITAL TRANSITION from September 2021

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Sarah Achermann	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Jeanet Bruil	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Patricia Clarke	Health Research Board	Ireland
Pablo del Río González	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Julio Diaz	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
José Paulo Esperança	Foundation for Science and Technology	Portugal
Marian Ferre	Spanish State Research Agency	Spain
Steven Heylen	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Krisztina Imrik	Eötvös Loránd Research Network	Hungary
Katarzyna Jarecka-Stępień	National Science Centre	Poland
Christiane Joerk	German Research Foundation	Germany
Christiane Kaell	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Marko Klobucar	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Paula Leskinen	Academy of Finland	Finland

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Philip Lorentzen	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Fernando Martín	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
Malin Mobjörk (Chair)	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development	Sweden
Oskar Otsus	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Anne-Hélène Prieur-Richard	French National Research Agency	France
Michael Ryan	Science Foundation Ireland	Ireland
Elena Simion	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania	Romania
Tobias B. Strøm	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Meike Teschke	German Research Foundation	Germany
Gabriella Verbovszky	Eötvös Loránd Research Network	Hungary
Valters Vētra	Latvian Science Council	Latvia
Sarah Webb	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Martin Winger	German Research Foundation	Germany
Science Europe Coordination	Nicola Francesco Dotti	

WORKING GROUP ON COMMUNICATION from September 2021

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Anneli Allik (Chair)	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Gundega Balode	Latvian Science Council	Latvia
Kim Barbé	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Benedikt Bastong	German Research Foundation	Germany
Elisabet Blomberg	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development	Sweden
Petr Chorošenin	Czech Science Foundation	Czech Republic
Nastassja Ekelöf	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life & Welfare	Sweden
Thomas Evensen	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Luís Ferreira	Foundation for Science and Technology	Portugal
Anna Maria Fleetwood	Swedish Research Council	Sweden
Jane Futrell	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Didier Goossens	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Ynte Hoekstra	Dutch Research Council	Netherlands
Vojtěch Janů	Czech Science Foundation	Czech Republic
Anna Korzekwa-Józefowicz	National Science Centre	Poland
Stefan Kranewitter	Austrian Science Fund	Austria
Dario Lecic	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Corinne Le Ny-Gigon	French National Research Agency	France
Ana Lončar	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Gillian Markey	Health Research Board	Ireland
Berta Martínez	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Marta Michalska-Bugajska	Foundation for Polish Science	Poland

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
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Lorna O'Driscoll	Science Foundation Ireland	Ireland
Inés Ortega	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
Jose Antonio Plaza	National Institute of Health Carlos III	Spain
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Pedro Serena	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Hilde Totland Harket	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Antonella Varaschin	National Institute for Nuclear Physics	Italy
Kata Veronika Tóth	Eötvös Loránd Research Network	Hungary
Eric Winnen	Fund for Scientific Research	Belgium
Science Europe Coordination	Valentina Garoia	

PROJECT TASK FORCE ON RECOGNITION SYSTEMS

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Aoife Cahill	Health Research Board	Ireland
Elena Domínguez	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Tobias Grimm	German Research Foundation	Germany
Christian Lund	Research Council of Norway	Norway
Antonio Masiero	National Institute for Nuclear Physics	Italy
Sandra Milovanović Soldatić	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Simon Ošo	Slovenian Research Agency	Slovenia
Abigail Reynolds	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Sean Sapcariu	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Ioana Spanache	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania	Romania
Science Europe Coordination	James Morris (Task Force Leader)	

PROJECT TASK FORCE ON MONITORING CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Gregory Absillis	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Jean-Luc Barras (Task Force Leader)	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Reinhard Belocky	Austrian Science Fund	Austria
Jasminka Boljević	Croatian Science Foundation	Croatia
Lidia Borrell-Damián	Science Europe	Belgium
Helena Burg	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Dominique Butt	UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
William Dinkel	German Research Foundation	Germany
Maura Hiney	Health Research Board	Ireland
Tom Jakobs	Luxembourg National Research Fund	Luxembourg
Monica Lanuza	Spanish National Research Council	Spain

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Marta Łazarowicz	Foundation for Polish Science	Poland
Honorata Plewńska	French National Research Agency	France
Kadri Raudvere	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Anna Strzebońska	National Science Centre	Poland
Laura Tejada	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Paulina Wojciechowska	National Science Centre	Poland
Science Europe Coordination	Mathilde Reumaux	

STAFF OF THE SCIENCE EUROPE OFFICE

NAME	TITLE
Lidia Borrell-Damián <i>Since September 2019</i>	Secretary General
Giorgia Battiato <i>Until February 2022</i>	Junior Communications Officer
Adrien Braem <i>Since October 2017</i>	Senior Policy Officer
Nicola Francesco Dotti <i>Since October 2021</i>	Senior Policy Officer
Maud Evrard <i>Until March 2021</i>	Head of Policy Affairs
Stephanie Flouquet <i>Since March 2021</i>	Personal and Administrative Assistant
Valentina Garoia <i>Since October 2021</i>	Communications Manager
Iwan Groeneveld <i>Since June 2015</i>	Events and Publications Officer
James Morris <i>Since July 2019</i>	Senior Policy Officer
Lauren O'Connor <i>Until September 2021</i>	Personal and Administrative Assistant
Mathilde Reumaux <i>Since July 2017</i>	Senior Policy Officer
Artemis Rodopoulou <i>Since August 2013</i>	Office Manager
Bregt Saenen <i>Since November 2021</i>	Senior Policy Officer
Lorna Stokes <i>Until August 2021</i>	Communications Manager
Marie Timmermann <i>Until August 2021</i>	Senior Policy Officer
Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch <i>Until March 2021</i>	Head of Research Affairs

SCIENCE EUROPE OPEN PUBLICATIONS 2021

TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
Science Europe as an organisation	
Science Europe 2020 Annual Report	May
Science Europe Strategy	June
Science Europe Multi-annual Action Plan	June
European Research Area	
Response to the EC Consultation on the Roadmap for a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe	May
Horizon Europe and the ERA Need All European Forces, Switzerland Included	July
An Inclusive ERA for Excellent Research – Reaction to the Proposed Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe	July
Open letter on ERA governance	October
An ERA Governance Fit for Purpose	November
Horizon Europe	
Science Europe Statement on Ensuring Collaboration with Non-EU Countries to Build Stronger European Research and Innovation	March
Open Letter of European STI Councils and Advisory Bodies and other Science Organisations on the Participation of Switzerland under Horizon Europe	June
Letter to President von der Leyen to support the Association of the UK to Horizon Europe	November
Research Data	
Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management – Extended Edition	January
Practical Guide on Sustainable Research Data	June
Q&A: Aligning Research Data Management Across Europe	June
Research Infrastructures	
Summary Report of the Research Infrastructures Satellite Workshop with the OECD-Global Science Forum: Research Infrastructures mobilisation in response to COVID-19: lessons learned	December
Open Access	
The Open Access Diamond Journals Study	March
Commentary on the FAIRsharing Data Repository Selection Proposal	March
The Rights Retention Strategy and publisher equivocation: an open letter to researchers (co-signatory)	April
Joint Position Statement on the Draft Data Repository Selection Criteria	April
Briefing Paper on Open Access Monitoring	May
Joint Statement with CESEAR and EUA on Empowering Researchers in Open Access	May
Investing in the Open Access Book infrastructure - A call for action (co-signatory)	May

TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
Digital Agenda	
Right Balance between Fostering Innovation and Trust Essential also for the Research Sector	July
Which Role for Research in the Future Data Act?	July
A set of European Digital Principles: Essential, but a Broader Approach is Needed	August
Research Plays an Essential Role in Public Interest Data Use	August
Research Culture	
Report on the results of the Scoping Questionnaire on Research Culture	June
Statement on Research Culture - Empowering Researchers with a Thriving Research System	November
Report of the 2021 High Level Workshop on the ERA	December
Green and Digital Transition	
Call to Action to Research Organisations for the Net-Zero Transition	November
Report of the 7 September Science Europe Policy Workshop 'Science for the Green Transition'	November
Covid-19	
Report of the GRC Regional Meeting of the European Region on COVID-19	May
Overview of activities from Science Europe Member Organisations to address the COVID-19 pandemic	December

SCIENCE EUROPE MAJOR EVENTS 2021

TITLE	DATE
Aligning Research Data Management Across Europe	27 January
Research Infrastructures Mobilisation in Response to COVID-19: Lessons Learned	11 May
Jointly towards Sustainable Research Data	2 June
Science for the Green Transition	7 September
2021 GRC European Regional Meeting	21-22 October
Science for Net-Zero Transition	8 November
Empowering Policy Makers with Informed Scientific Knowledge to Address the Climate Crisis	10 November
High Level Workshop on Research Culture in the ERA: Ensuring the attractiveness of the research sector for current and future generations	24 November

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Science Europe is the association of major research funding and research performing organisations in Europe.

Our vision is for a European Research Area with optimal conditions, to support robust education, research and innovation systems.

We define long-term perspectives for European research and champion best-practice approaches that enable high-quality research for knowledge advancement and the needs of society.

We are uniquely placed to lead advancements to the European Research Area and inform global developments through participation in research initiatives where science is a strong and trusted component of sustainable economic, environmental, and societal development.

More information is available at www.scienceeurope.org

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